

Reflections of Globalization in Education: Metaphorical Perceptions of Social Studies Teacher Candidates

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Abstract

This study, which aims to determine the metaphorical perceptions of social studies teacher candidates regarding the concept of globalization, was conducted using the phenomenological research design, one of the qualitative research designs. The study group consisted of 101 teacher candidates enrolled in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th grades of the Social Studies Education Department at Afyon Kocatepe University's Faculty of Education. To determine social studies teacher candidates' metaphorical perceptions of the concept of globalization, a form containing the statement "Globalization is like... because..." was used. The analysis of the collected data was conducted using content analysis. It was determined that the teacher candidates developed 156 metaphors related to the concept of globalization, and these metaphors were categorized into five conceptual categories. The identified conceptual categories are integration, negativity, interaction, change, and technology.

Keywords: Globalization, Education, Social Sciences, Metaphor,

Introduction

The concept of globalization is a new term that describes an old process. The beginning of global economic integration actually dates back five hundred years to the European colonial period. However, this process has accelerated in the last quarter century as a result of developments in technology and communication systems, the removal of barriers to trade, and the increase in the political and economic power of multinational companies (Ellwood, 2003). Globalization has different meanings for several reasons. First, due to the interaction of intercultural relations, we can speak of the existence of cultural globalization (Ağcakaya and Ögrekçi, 2016). In general, globalization encompasses the spread and development of economic, social, and political relations between countries, increased capital mobility, the resolution of ideological divisions, better understanding of different social cultures, beliefs, and expectations, and intensified relations between countries. In globalization, education is a process that enables continuous learning, knowing information, being knowledgeable, producing information, and living with information (Dağlı, 2007). Although there is no common consensus on what elements the concept of globalization should include, Cebeci (2011) defines globalization as the integration of people, capital, technology, and services. Adams (2008) defines globalization as the increasing integration of the world as a result of increased trade, direct foreign investment, and the implementation of intellectual property rights, which have led to greater mobility of production factors.

Globalization can be defined as a phenomenon that has developed in parallel with changes in communication and transportation technologies, bringing humanity closer together. This phenomenon has had a profound impact on all areas, including education (Kan, 2020). Social Studies, a subject that concerns the sociocultural dimension of education and

encompasses many scientific fields, has been significantly influenced by globalization in terms of its objectives, content, and teaching processes. With the impact of globalization, the Social Studies course has shifted its focus toward instilling common global values in students through teaching programs (Aslan, 2016). In this context, the idea of cultivating global citizens who feel responsible not only toward their own countries but also toward all of humanity and possess a universal consciousness has begun to be discussed (Kan, 2020). The general objective of Social Studies is to cultivate good citizens. The citizens we seek to cultivate cannot be isolated from global developments and changes. This is because the fundamental objective of education is to prepare individuals for these developments and changes. The Social Studies course also aims to nurture active and participatory citizens who are ready for change and able to adapt to developments. The vision of the Social Studies program, as stated, and the concept of citizenship that it seeks to impart, has both national and universal characteristics. This is because cultivating citizens who possess “fundamental democratic values,” “human rights,” and “environmental awareness” requires imparting universal knowledge, skills, and experiences (MEB, 2005).

When examining the Social Studies curriculum in Turkey, it is evident that global issues were partially addressed in the 1998 Social Studies curriculum. However, in the 2005 Social Studies curriculum, which was prepared by drawing on the basic principles developed by the National Council for the Social Studies (NCSS) for Social Studies education, the “Global Connections” learning area was included for the first time (MEB, 2005). According to the NCSS (2005), the fundamental purpose of social studies is to help young people develop the ability to make conscious and rational decisions in a democratic society with cultural differences in an interdependent world. The phrase “interdependent world” emphasized in this generally accepted definition of Social Studies brings the concept of globalization to the fore (Gökpınar, 2019). In this context, it is important to raise students who think globally while they are still in school. Social Studies can be used to raise individuals who take responsibility on a global scale and are capable of forming attitudes (Tezcan, 2002). In order to teach students about globalization in a correct and healthy manner, teachers must first have a good understanding of this phenomenon. This study aims to determine the metaphorical perceptions of Social Studies teacher candidates, who are the teachers of the future, regarding the concept of globalization.

When reviewing the relevant literature, it is observed that there are not many studies on globalization in the field of social studies. Among the studies conducted, studies examining the reflections of globalization, global citizenship, and global connections in social studies textbooks (Gökpınar, 2019; Çakar, 2008; Sağlam et al., 2011; Özyurt, 2009; Şimşek, 2008; Dere and Uçar, 2020; Ulu, 2015). There are studies that examine the perceptions and views of social studies teachers or teacher candidates regarding globalization and global citizenship (Öztürk and Günel, 2016; Çermik, 2015; Çolak, 2015; Göl, 2013; Balbağ, 2016). When reviewing the relevant literature, it is important to note that there are no studies examining the metaphorical perceptions of Social Studies teacher candidates regarding the concept of globalization, which highlights the importance of this research in filling this gap in the literature.

The study sought to answer the following questions regarding the examination of social studies teacher candidates' metaphorical perceptions of the concept of globalization:

1. What metaphors do social studies teacher candidates use to explain their perceptions of the concept of “globalization”?
2. What categories do the metaphors put forward by university students regarding the concept of “globalization” fall under in terms of their common characteristics?

Method

Research Design

This study utilized the qualitative research design known as “phenomenology.” Phenomenology focuses on phenomena that we are aware of but do not have a deep and detailed understanding of. Phenomenology provides an appropriate research framework for studies that aim to investigate phenomena that are not entirely unfamiliar to us but whose full meaning we do not yet grasp (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2016).

Study Group

The working group for this study consists of 101 prospective teachers who were studying Social Studies Education at a state university during the fall semester of 2021-2022 and were selected using a convenient sampling method. The convenient sampling method was chosen because it is inexpensive, involves a group of participants familiar to the researcher, and makes the research faster and more practical (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2016).

Data Collection and Analysis

In order to reveal the metaphors that social studies teacher candidates participating in the study had regarding the concept of globalization, each teacher candidate was given a blank piece of paper with the phrase “Globalization is like ... because ...” written on it. The students were asked to express one or two thoughts using this phrase. By including the word “because” in the sentence, the Social Studies teacher candidates participating in the study were asked to provide reasons for their metaphors. The teacher candidates were given approximately 20 minutes to write their own metaphors related to the concept of “globalization.” The compositions written by the teacher candidates serve as documents and records, forming the primary data source for this research.

To begin analyzing the data, the teacher candidates' answer sheets were first checked to see if they had been filled out in accordance with the purpose of the study. Content analysis, one of the data evaluation methods frequently used in qualitative research, was used to analyze the data. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2016), the main purpose of content analysis is to reveal the underlying truths within the collected data. To this end, content analysis involves grouping similar data under defined themes and organizing and interpreting them in a way that is understandable to the reader. The collected data were analyzed separately by two people. The results of the analysis were compared. The reliability of the research data was calculated using the formula $\text{Consensus} / (\text{Consensus} + \text{Disagreement}) * 100$, as proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), and a 96% consensus was achieved. The parts where there was disagreement were evaluated together, and a consensus was reached.

Findings

Data on the metaphors produced by the teacher candidates participating in the study and their frequencies are presented in tables in order.

Table 1: Metaphors for the concept of globalization

Order	Metaphor	f	Order	Metaphor	f
1	Integration	16	55	Avalanche	1
2	Development	6	56	Destruction	1
3	The end of the world	6	57	Socialization	1
4	Development	6	58	Friendship	1
5	Communication	4	59	Pool	1
6	World	3	60	A small village	1

7	Sun	3	61	Economy	1
8	Interaction	3	62	Finding common ground	1
9	Change	3	63	Rainbow	1
10	Technology	3	64	Language	1
11	Disease	2	65	Shopping	1
12	Communication with the world	2	66	Exchange of information	1
13	Culturalization	2	67	Epidemic disease	1
14	Shopping	2	68	Universe	1
15	Globalization	2	69	Spread	1
16	Factory	1	70	Ivy	1
17	Mixture	1	71	Laughter	1
18	Information	1	72	Human	1
19	Uniformity	1	73	Keeping up with the times	1
20	School	1	74	Expatriates	1
21	Anthill	1	75	The sprouting of a seed	1
22	Sea	1	76	Bus	1
23	Technological process	1	77	Phoenix	1
24	Football team	1	78	Eternity	1
25	Puzzle piece	1	79	Water cycle	1
26	Sheep in a flock	1	80	Global process	1
27	Students	1	81	Culture	1
28	Stars in the sky	1	82	Covid-19	1
29	Food	1	83	Modernization	1
30	Family environment	1	84	Telephone	1
31	Book	1	85	Integration	1
32	Matryoshka	1	86	Global village	1
33	Intertwined bond	1	87	Universalization	1
34	Worldview	1	88	People being close to each other	1
35	Friendship	1	89	Digitalization	1
36	Double-edged sword	1	90	Internet	1
37	Cancer	1	91	Scientification	1
38	Empty classroom	1	92	Information age	1
39	Glaciers	1	93	Technological life	1
40	Deep sleep	1	94	Water	1
41	Life	1	95	Pen	1
42	Black hole	1	96	Virus	1
43	Killer	1	97	Time	1
44	Empty glass	1	98	Deadly virus	1
45	Desert	1	99	Revolution	1
46	Endangered animals	1	100	Investment	1
47	Killer's weapon	1	101	Walnut	1
48	Sign of the apocalypse	1	102	Socialism	1
49	Massacre	1	103	Monarchy	1
50	Swamp	1	104	Medicine	1
51	Beehive	1	105	Return to prehistoric times	1
52	Ant hill	1	106	Love	1
53	Knot	1	107	Diamond	1
54	Mirror	1	108	Becoming a phenomenon	1
Total					156

Social studies teacher candidates produced a total of 156 valid metaphors related to the concept of globalization. Of the 156 metaphors, 93 were proposed by one person. These include: Factory, Mixture, Information, Uniformity, School, Ant Hill, Sea, Technological Process, Football Team, Puzzle Piece, Sheep in a Flock, Students, Stars in the Sky, Food, Family Environment, Book, Matryoshka, Interconnected Bond, Worldview, Friendship, Double-edged knife, Cancer, Empty classroom, Glaciers, Deep sleep, Life, Black hole, Killer, Empty glass, Desert, Endangered animals, Killer's weapon, Sign of the apocalypse, Massacre, Swamp, Beehive, Ant nest, Knot, Mirror, Avalanche, Destruction, Socialization, Friendship,

Pool, Small village, Economy, Finding common ground, Rainbow, Language, Shopping, Information exchange, Epidemic, Universe, Spread, Ivy, Laughter, Human, Keeping up with the times, Expatriates, A seed sprouting, Bus, Phoenix, Infinity, Water cycle, Global process, Culture, Covid-19, Modernization, Telephone, Integration, Global village, Universalization, People being close, Digitalization, Internet, Scientification, Information age, Technological life, Water, Pen, Virus, Time, A deadly virus, Revolution, Investment, Walnut, Socialism, Monarchy, Medicine, Return to the prehistoric era, Love, Diamond, and Phenomenon.

The number of students who produced the remaining metaphors ranged from 2 to 16. These were: Integration (16), Development (6), The end of the world (6), Development (6), Communication (4), World (3), Sun (3), Interaction (3), Change (3), Technology (3), Disease (2), Communication with the World (2), Acculturation (2), Shopping (2), and Globalization (2).

Table 2: Themes of metaphors related to the concept of globalization

Theme	Metaphors	Metaphor frequency	Number of metaphors
1. Integration	Unity/Togetherness (16), World (3), Globalization (2), Mirror (1), Factory (1), Mixture (1), Information (1), Uniformity (1), School (1), Ant Hill (1), Sea (1), Technological Process (1), Football Team (1), Puzzle Piece (1), Sheep in a Flock (1), Students (1), Stars in the sky (1), Food (1), Family environment (1), Book (1), Matryoshka (1), Intertwined bond (1), Worldview (1), Friendship (1), Walnut (1), Knot (1), Beehive (1)	55	27
2. Negativity	The end of the world (6), Sun (3), Disease (2), Virus (2), Double-edged knife (1), Cancer (1), Empty classroom (1), Glaciers (1), Deep sleep (1), Life (1), A black hole (1), Murderer (1), Empty glass (1), Desert (1), Endangered animals (1), Murderer's weapon (1), Sign of the apocalypse (1), Massacre (1), Swamp (1), Avalanche (1), Destruction (1), Water (1), Revolution (1), Kingdom (1), Return to the prehistoric age (1), Diamond (1)	34	26
3. Interaction	Communication (4), Interaction (3), Acculturation (2), Shopping (2), Communication with the world (2), Socialization (1), Friendship (1), Swimming pool (1), Small village (1), Economy (1), Finding common ground (1), Rainbow (1), Language (1), Trade (1), Exchange of information (1), Epidemic disease (1), Universe (1), Spread (1), Ivy (1), Laughter (1) Integration (1), Global village (1), Universalization (1), People being close (1), Becoming a phenomenon (1)	35	25
4. Change	Change (3), Human (1), Keeping up with the times (1), Expatriates (1), The sprouting of a seed (1), Bus (1), Phoenix (1), Eternity (1), Water Cycle (1), Global Process (1), Culture (1), Covid-19, Socialism (1), Love (1) Development (6), Phone (2), Modernization (1), Pen (1), Time (1), Investment (1), Medicine (1)	29	21
5. Technology	Technology (3), Digitalization (1), Internet (1), Scientification (1), Information age (1), Technological life (1)	8	6

The 156 metaphors produced by social studies teacher candidates regarding the concept of globalization were examined under five themes.

1. Integration

A total of 26 different metaphors were identified in the integration theme. The frequency of repetition of these metaphors was determined to be 53. In this category, Unity/Togetherness (16), World (3), Globalization (2), Mirror (1), Factory (1), Mixture (1), Knowledge (1), Uniformity (1), School (1), Ant Hill (1), Sea (1), Technological Process (1), Football Team (1),

Puzzle Piece (1), Sheep in a Flock (1), Students (1), Stars in the sky (1), Food (1), Family environment (1), Book (1), Matryoshka (1), An intertwined bond (1), Worldview (1), Friendship (1), Walnut (1), Knot (1), Beehive (1). Participant ÖA.2, who developed the metaphor of “togetherness” in relation to the concept of globalization, explained the metaphorical aspect with the sentence, *“Globalization is the coming together of people and societies with the removal of borders.”* Participant ÖA.6, who developed the “world” metaphor, explained the analogy by saying, *“With globalization, we have come to a single world.”* Participant ÖA.15, who developed the ‘factory’ metaphor, explained the analogy by saying, *“When we look at the world, it is as if we are all working in the same factory.”*

2. Negativity

A total of 26 different metaphors were identified in the theme of negativity. The frequency of repetition of these metaphors was determined to be 34. In this category, the end of the world (6), the sun (3), disease (2), virus (2), double-edged sword (1), cancer (1), Empty classroom (1), Glaciers (1), Deep sleep (1), Life (1), A black hole (1), Killer (1), Empty glass (1), Desert (1), Endangered animals (1), Killer's weapon (1), Sign of the apocalypse (1), Massacre (1), Swamp (1), Avalanche (1), Destruction (1), Water (1), Revolution (1), Kingdom (1), Return to the prehistoric age (1), Diamond (1) are included. Participant ÖA.20, who developed the metaphor of “the end of the world” in relation to the concept of globalization, explained the analogy with the sentence, *“With the development of technology, nothing remains hidden anymore. While so much technological development is good on the one hand, on the other hand, it brings about the end of the world.”* Participant ÖA.9, who developed the metaphor of a “deep well,” explained the metaphorical aspect with the statement, *“Developments in areas such as technology, transportation, and communication may make it easier to access information and distant lands, but this rapid development resembles a bottomless well and is frightening.”* The participant who developed the metaphor of “the murderer's weapon,” ÖA.30, explained the metaphorical aspect with the statement, *“The world is increasingly uniting, borders are disappearing, and it seems as if we are being controlled by a single hand, and they are using this like a murderer's weapon.”*

3. Interaction

It was determined that there are 24 different metaphors in the interaction theme. The frequency of repetition of these metaphors was determined to be 32. In this category, Communication (4), Interaction (3), Acculturation (2), Shopping (2), Communication with the World (2), Socialization (1), Friendship (1), Pool (1), Small Village (1), Economy (1), Meeting on Common Ground (1), Rainbow (1), Language (1), Shopping (1), Information Exchange (1), Epidemic (1), Universe (1), Spread (1), Ivy (1), Laughter (1) Integration (1), Global village (1), Universalization (1), People being close (1), Becoming a phenomenon (1) are included. Participant ÖA.51, who developed the metaphor of “interaction” in relation to the concept of globalization, explained the analogy by saying, *“Just as individuals interact within society, globalization brings the whole world into interaction.”* Participant ÖA.60, who developed the metaphor of “socialization,” explained the analogy by saying, *“Thanks to globalization, people come into contact with different cultures more often.”* The participant who developed the metaphor of “friendship,” ÖA.70, explained the analogy by saying, *“Globalization causes people, societies, and cultures to form closeness, understanding, and bonds, that is, to become friends.”*

4. Change

It was determined that there were 21 different metaphors in the theme of change. The frequency of repetition of these metaphors was determined to be 29. In this category, Change (3), Human (1), Keeping up with the times (1), Expatriates (1), The sprouting of a seed (1), Bus (1), Phoenix (1), Infinity (1), Water Cycle (1), Global Process (1), Culture (1), Covid-19, Socialism (1), Love (1), Development (6), Telephone (2), Modernization (1), Pen (1), Time (1), Investment (1), Medicine (1). Participant ÖA.40, who developed the metaphor of “change” in relation to the concept of globalization, explained the metaphorical aspect with the sentence, *“Globalization can be described as the transformation of societies in every aspect.”* Participant ÖA.68, who developed the metaphor of “the sprouting of a seed,” explained the metaphorical aspect with the sentence, *“Globalization is not an event that will happen overnight. I see it as a seed falling to the ground and sprouting over time; it develops slowly but deeply.”*

5. Technology

Six different metaphors were identified in the theme of technology. The frequency of repetition of these metaphors was determined to be 8. This category includes Technology (3), Digitalization (1), Internet (1), Scientification (1), Information Age (1), and Technological Life (1). Participant ÖA.33, who developed the “technology” metaphor related to the concept of globalization, explained the analogy by stating, *“Globalization can be described as the transformation of societies in every aspect.”* The participant who developed the “internet” metaphor, ÖA.88, explained the metaphorical aspect with the statement, *“Thanks to the internet, we can access the information we want very quickly; in a globalizing world, accessing everything has become very easy.”*

Conclusion, Discussion, and Recommendations

When examining social studies teacher candidates' metaphorical perceptions of globalization, their responses were divided into five themes. These themes are integration, negativity, interaction, change, and technology. It was found that teacher candidates used responses related to the theme of integration the most.

When the data obtained is examined, the metaphors in the interaction category are listed as Communication, Interaction, Acculturation, Shopping, Communicating with the world, Socialization, Friendship, Pool, Small village, Economy, Meeting on common ground, Rainbow, Language, Shopping, Information exchange, Epidemic, Universe, Spreading, Ivy, Laughter, Integration, Global Village, Universalization, People Being Close, and Phenomenon. It was observed that the most developed metaphors in this category were “communication (f=4)” and “interaction (f=3).” When examining the participants' views, they emphasized that they are in constant interaction with each other in terms of communication, socialization, and exchange related to the concept of globalization in the interaction category. Similar explanations have been made in studies by Toprak and Çelik (2022) and Toulmin (1999), stating that many phenomena around the world are not limited to a single country but affect all nations. This situation reveals that, thanks to globalization, people living in many different parts of the world come together and interact, presenting different perspectives on various issues and acquiring new knowledge. Ess and Sudweeks (2001), in their study, have shown that with the advancement of technology, the world is becoming increasingly smaller compared to the past, and it has become easier and faster to obtain information about people and cultures. In addition,

McLuhan and Powers (2020) emphasize in their studies that the concepts of time and space have lost their importance and that many situations occur simultaneously.

When the data obtained is examined, it is seen that the other category identified is technology. The metaphors in this category are listed as Technology, Digitalization, Internet, Scientification, Information Age, and Technological Life. It is seen that the most developed metaphor in this category is “technology (f=3)”. Considering the metaphors developed by teacher candidates, it can be said that globalization has been facilitated and borders have been eliminated thanks to technology. Therefore, it can be emphasized that instant access to information, news, and events is now possible. Similar to these results, Tanrıöver and Kırılı (2015) state that with these developments in science and technology, the advancements in digital technology, particularly the internet, enable individuals to access the information and entertainment they desire and socialize through computers or other technological devices without being tied to a specific location. They also note that people are able to make their voices heard on a global scale in this process and that they are both sources and recipients in this process. Other studies that highlight the importance of technology in globalization, such as Adıgüzel (2011) and Toprak and Çelik (2022), have shown that technology has brought the globalization process to this level. In the study by Hytten and Bettez (2008), it was determined that the concept of technology is at the forefront in the definition of globalization and that the working group associates globalization with technology.

When the data obtained was examined, the metaphors in the integration category were Unity/Togetherness, World, Globalization, Mirror, Factory, Mixture, Information, Uniformity, School, Ant Hill, Sea, Technological Process, Football Team, Puzzle Piece, Sheep in a Flock, Students, Stars in the Sky, Food, Family Environment, Book, Matryoshka, Intertwined Bond, Worldview, Friendship, Walnut, Knot, and Beehive. It was observed that the most developed metaphor in this category was “unity/togetherness (f=16).” A review of the literature reveals similar results in the study conducted by Toprak and Çelik (2022). In this study, when the participants' explanations and metaphors were examined, it was revealed that globalization was approached as a whole composed of parts, and that any situation affecting one part would affect all parts. Therefore, the phenomenon we call globalization can actually be expressed as the union of individual parts on a global scale. In addition, in a study conducted by Ezer and Aksüt (2021) with social studies teacher candidates, the teacher candidates expressed their thoughts as technological developments connecting and uniting people who are far apart from each other. McLuhan and Powers (2020), on the other hand, stated that as a result of technological developments, the world has become smaller and more concentrated, and the interdependence between people has increased. Çelik Varol and Varol (2019) describe globalization as people becoming more connected to each other through technology.

When the data obtained is examined, metaphors in the negative category include The end of the world, Sun, Disease, Virus, Double-edged sword, Cancer, Empty classroom, Glaciers, Deep sleep, Life, Black hole, Killer, An Empty Glass, Desert, Endangered Animals, The Killer's Weapon, Sign of the Apocalypse, Massacre, Swamp, An Avalanche, Destruction, Water, Revolution, Kingdom, Return to the Prehistoric Age, and Diamond. It was observed that the most frequently developed metaphor in this category was “the end of the world (f=6).” When the opinions are examined, the association of the concept of globalization with negativity is parallel to the results obtained in the study conducted by Akhan and Kaymak (2021). In this study, when teachers' opinions on the concept of globalization are examined, it can be said that there are teachers who see globalization as imperialism and colonialism. In addition, Öztürk and Günel's (2016) study also shows that social studies teachers view globalization as the dominance of dominant powers over underdeveloped countries, indicating a negative perspective on the concept. Similarly, in a study conducted by Balay (2004), it can be said that

globalization empties concepts such as independence, national values, and national sovereignty of their meaning, disregards national borders, and legitimizes imperialism under the name of globalization.

When the data obtained is examined, metaphors in the category of change include Change, Human, Keeping up with the times, Expatriates, The sprouting of a seed, Bus, Phoenix, Eternity, Water cycle, A global process, Culture, Covid-19, Socialism, Love, Development, Telephone, Modernization, Pen, Time, Investment, Medicine. It was observed that the most developed metaphor in this category was “change (f=3).” When the opinions obtained are examined, it can be said that teacher candidates put forward positive opinions. In the study conducted by Akhan and Kaymak (2021), it is seen that some teachers define globalization as “all kinds of change and development experienced on a large scale.”

Recommendations:

- This study is limited to Social Studies teacher candidates studying at a state university; the research can be applied to other teacher candidates as well.
- The research only included teacher candidates; the research can be applied to Social Studies teachers who are currently working.

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